

Journal Homepage: <https://edurekhapublisher.com/erijalss/>

Volume- 1 Issue- 4 (November-December) 2025

ISSN: 3107-5169 (Online)

Frequency: Bimonthly

PAGES: 16-19

ARTICLE TITLE:

The Research of Economic GDP and High-Technique Products' Behavior & its Judgment on Scientists Sustainably & Continually

Run Xu¹, Xiangying Zhu², Zhekui Quan³, Huiling Jin⁴, Zhe Piao⁵, Wanhao Wu⁶, Yonggen Wu⁷, Guanghui Yu⁸, Jinsong Zhang⁹, Tianyi Yan¹⁰, Yanjie Mu¹¹, Gonghai Yu¹², Qinghua Qu¹³, Yinglan Li¹⁴, Yinghua Li¹⁵, Hua Li¹⁶, Changfu Jin¹⁷, Xianglan Piao¹⁸, Junhao Xu¹⁹, Xiangyu Qi²⁰

^{1,2,3,4,5} Gyeongsang National University, School of Nano New Materials Engineering, Jinju-Si 52828, Gyeongnam-Do, Korea

^{1,6,7,8} Yantai Institute of Science & Technology, Yantai 264005, Shandong Province, China

^{9,10} Jeonbuk University, Dept. of Business & administration, Jeonju-Si 54896, Jeonlabuk-Do, South Korea

^{11,12,13} Hanzhong International Exchange Ltd., corp., Yantai 264000, Shandong Province, China

^{14,15,16} Xien Xi High-Technology Ltd., Corp., Shenzhen 518134, Guangdong Province, China

^{17,18} Yanbian University, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Yanji 133000, Jilin Province, China

¹⁹ Zhejiang Chinese Medical University, Dept. of the Clinic Medicine, Hangzhou 311402, Zhejiang Province, China

²⁰ Northwest Polytechnical University, Faculty of Aero Materials Science & Engineering, Xi'an 710072, Shanxi Province, China

Abstract

With regards to the high-tech skill and products the research on them will become necessary and important currently by Scientists who has pursued those high-tech searching for producing innovation product urgently. So that we may participate in the new machine even robot service expenses which may bring out many new idea and method for us to continuously push those innovation products forwards sustainably. Therefore, the new employment will be realized for those graduates from college annually and meanwhile, the high-tech product supply chains can carry out many new opportunities gradually and eventually. There will be a much more big space in the huge chains which is not neglected at all though they may process one special part there is still many those OEMs (original equipment manufacturers) for making a final product completion at the down-stream makers. As we knew the hundred parts will assemble one complete product, so the technique transfers to the up-stream OEM will be important which we are named the technology transfer for their survival to look for more working chances. On the other side, the scientist will still be publishing their achievement on a famous journal for us to identify and use which can shorten down our research time and times for the sake of being convenient to use on our research to create another product in time. Thereby, the relevant scientists must create more innovation product diagram plan with detailing description to look at whether it is about to realize into product for our citizen sharing and continuously developing. The producing, study, research and application should become a series of procedure transformed to out senior engineers in order to make a decision to produce besides conveying to general manager and administrative senior manager. Certainly, the proposal of the entire industrial business would advocate those innovation

EDU REKHA INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTS, LAW AND SOCIAL SCIENCE (ERIJALSS)

Law & social science, anthropology, business studies, communication studies, corporate governance, criminology, cross-cultural studies, demography, development studies, economics, education, ethics geography, history, industrial relations, information science, international relations, law, health, linguistics

JOIN US

+91 8638576262

edurekhapublisher.com

ARTICLE HISTORY

RECEIVED
10-11-2025

ACCEPTED
16-11-2025

PUBLISHED
20-11-2025

Corresponding author:

Run Xu¹

product in order to reduce the risky burden in the case of conditions of low-cost and competition one.

Keywords: research; economic development; GDP (gross domestic product) enhancement; scientists; high-technique product; sustainably; behavior & judgment

1. Introduction

In current society the high-technique products will be dominated in others to become a strong force to push the society to develop continuously and sustainably, so the scientist and scholars will become an important factor to play in every place to proceed the relevant research and study on the hot point frequently. So that publishing achievement papers may provide a strong force to support the future life-level like climate change and public sanitation for benefiting the world human in future. We should go on searching for innovation papers include in the latest high-technique product research like clean energy and new one to push many lots of skill to make different cutting-edge-field product continually. As we knew the current climate problem will be derived from the contaminating factory and automobile, so the new energy should occupy the first significant position for our scholar & scientist and experts to sustainably search and make measure to solve it from variation views which may help us to think about more factors to replace the problems mutually. We might align the measure from one view to different one to proceed simulate to judge the first and the second even third method to solve it for the sake of once happening the problem accident there will be another method to replace it in urgency. [1~6] So we put our eyes too long not only viewing the current status but also looking at the longer years like fairy tale cinema which provide future world several hundred years later. We may interest in those splendid scenery and consider the usefulness and make some experiments to trial the feasibility, like the flight automobile which pass by the high buildings and make a dormitory in the one. There will not earth surface auto and all the auto can become flight one which is a future plan by USA fairy cinema maker. There may be not contamination gas and all of atmosphere is electric power and hydrogen fuel even small nuclear reaction pile as an engine. So we must emphasize the current energy exploitation and found so as to predict to make a plan to prepare the future infrastructure and write more paper with innovation method to arouse the future contribution. With the GDP(gross domestic product) enhancement we should not avoid to enter the ideal world with many robots in AI(artificial intelligence) software and automobiles with intelligent driving time many decades years later, so we prepare to afford the controlling skill to fix robots logical life and automobile matters with those high energy fuel. As to the former the controlling will be proceeding from now on and its equipment needs to enter our live life many years later and the latter will experience safe driving course with no accident. Those problems will must think about by us in advance or the error ones and accident may occur by then. [7~8]

2. Discussions

The qualified one may be appointed to be a associate professor and senior researcher to take a burden to educate the MS (Master of Science) & PhD (Philosophy of Doctor) degree continuously. Because they had some and much opportunities to complete the relevant projects singly and collaboratively which belongs to the high-tech product experimental and theoretical deduction. Thereby those ones includes in many innovative methods and calculations correspondingly. At the same time, the reports and papers will be submitted to the Fund commission which may be speared through the

relevant scientists. Meanwhile, the data with GDP and sale number would be analyzed for the sake of requesting according behavior & its following judgment by our scientist and fellows sustainably because they can grasp the economic phenomenon and its following explanation definitely and absolutely in advance through their endeavour in post-doctorate and after work-stations. [9~21]

2.1 Canadian & Chinese top provinces GDP analysis

The Canada and China top 4~9 provinces would display 18~14 billion dollars in light of Figure 1 in 1991 where the variation times might arrive at 1.3 times maximum with small one.

Figure 1 The Chinese top 4~9 provinces GDP analysis. [3]

Meanwhile, the Canada and China top three provinces would display 600~18 billion dollars in light of Figure 2 in 1991 by Canada~Hubei province where the variation times might arrive at 32 times maximum with large one to explain the large advantage of economic entity by Canada. In addition, the Taipei exceeded 200 billion dollars following Canada to occupy the second position while the three ones in China retained 28~18.8 billion dollars.

Figure 2 The Canada & the Chinese top 3 provinces GDP analysis. [3]

2.2 The global PC sale amount

The global PC (personal computer) sale amount and y-y value will display 365~275 million and 15.5%~4% by 2021~2025E respectively in terms of Figure 3 whose variation time might attain 1.3 times and

3.8 times with maximum expressed the declining tendency. [4] Meantime, the lowest sale amount and y-y value might attain 260 million in 2023 and -16% in 2022 respectively to explain the depressive situation then. According to the economist prediction the one in 2025 will afford 275 million and 4% y-y with a little increasing to compare with 2024. [4] It is judged that the reason for the maximum sale which would attain 365 million in 2021 is warehouse amount maintaining highest level with cheaper sell due to COVID (corona virus disease)-2019 pandemic term's with maximum. From the figure data it was observed that the minimum y-y might appear in 2022 while in 2023 it appeared the minimum sale, which explain the y-y definite tendency already in one year ago and then the sale attained that point next year namely in 2023.

Figure 3 The global PC sale amount and y-y.

2.3 International Journal of Engineering Inventions subject introduction

International Journal of Engineering Inventions (IJEI) is peer reviewed International Journal. IJEI publishes original research articles, review articles and technical notes. IJEI offers worldwide indexing to all published papers with IJEI. We are welcoming all the authors from the world to submit their cherish paper to this journal. At the same time, the peer-reviewed IJEI Journal is started with a mission to encourage contribution to research in Science and Technology. Encourage and motivate researchers in challenging areas of Sciences and Technology. There are the simplified rules for author to comply.

1. Submit your paper in MS Word (.doc or .docx) as per manuscript guidelines;
2. IJEI also provides hard copy of certificates to all authors free of cost at their postal address;
3. Publish both online as well as print version both;
4. Engineering & Science Technology;

On the other hand, the IJEI is majorly indexing like Google Scholar, Issue, Academia, Research Gate, Index Copernicus, Jour Info, ANED, ESCI World etc. [5]

2.4 Venezuela & four municipalities in China GDP analysis

The Venezuela & Chinese four municipalities GDP would exhibit 16.6~0.6 billion dollars by Venezuela and Chongqing municipality in 1972 in light of Figure 4 where the variation arrived 27.5 times with maximum explaining the Venezuela strong strength in economy then correspondingly. Meanwhile, the y-y in 1972 could attain 16~0% by them accordingly to explain the former potential force. In addition, there were three ones whose GDP surpassed 1 billion dollars and they would become Venezuela, Shanghai & Beijing and the former two of them were Venezuela & Shanghai GDP exceeded 2 billion dollars still. Moreover the former variation even maintained 6.4 times expressed

the Venezuela strong economy status then. On contrast, the Shanghai, Beijing & Tianjin retained 2.5~0.9% y-y in 1972 per year whose value maintained the middle position to express their stabilized economy development.

Figure 4 The Venezuela & Chinese four municipalities GDP analysis. [6]

2.5 Subject introduction of the International Journal of Arts and Social Science

Our website is the www.ijassjournal.com with ISSN: 2581-7922. Therein, the submission open for September 2025 Issue for the Volume 08 Issue 09. With regards to the professor & researcher, the International Journal of Arts and Social Science (IJASS) is an international journal which aims at meeting all the needs of diverse sections of people in the areas of Humanities and Social Studies. Meanwhile, the International Journal of Arts and Social Science is a journal that publishes articles which contribute new novel experimentation and theoretical work in all areas of Humanities and Social Science and its applications. The journal welcomes publications of high quality papers on theoretical developments and practical humanities and social science. We welcome to submitting the professor & researchers to our journals who send your paper to us promptly. So that we request you to submit your papers on or before September 20, 2025. Meantime, to inform the paper submission deadline will be the September 20, 2025 and the acceptance & rejection notification can be 5 to 6 days while the paper online publication time may be the September 30, 2025. On the other side, the IJASS aims to cover the latest outstanding developments in the field of engineering and computer science but not limited to the following branches, [7] They will be the Anthropology, Art, Communication studies, Corporate governance, Criminology, Cross-cultural Studies, Demography, Development studies, Economics, Education, English Literature, Ethics, Geography, History, Human Right Law, Human Rights, Human Factor, Industrial Relations, Information Science, Law, Linguistics, Library Science, Media Studies, Methodology, Philosophy, Political Science, Population Studies, Psychology, Public administration, Sociology, Social Welfare, Translation Studies, Women Studies, If you have any query or suggestion feel free contact us. Thereby, we would like to request you for forward this e-mail to group of your Friends/Students/ Staff /Colleagues / Associates/ Fellow Researchers, who may be benefited out of this.

2.6 The stocks change

The <Qingshan Zhiye> realized six plates in seven days; <Meibang Clothes> completed two continual plates; <Tainci Materials> increased limite; <Duofu Duo> impacted still the plate. [8] On the other hand, the Sep. 1 teaching buy code was 603083 <Cambrige Tech> buy point would be 94~95.9 yuan with the choosing logic which could be Huawei AI industrial chain &algorithm force whose institutions enhanced from ten to 228 ones. [9] On the other side, the special team tactic includes in following. 1. Team work. There are analytical division, tactic division and operating diversity co-operation; 2. Speciality. The constitution unions investigation, and speciality message to share; 3. Eye-light. Understanding the main behavior and management layer's market management intention; 4. Operation plates. Making picture to show the customers in order to enhance &attract capital kept up. [10]

3. Conclusions

The scientist will complete their research and development continuously in light of aligning their duties on work and their interesting effect, so they must publish their achievement in the latest journal constantly. Only those they may make progress and improve the theoretical and experimental result with inducing mathematics formula to exploring new method and some not referred places for the sake of progressing some innovation paths sustainably to the inferiority common expense by transforming their results into product in manufacturers eventually. Thereby, there will be many things for us to do with innovation mind and methods which may be quicker than the formal ones, and then publish their cherish achievement in famous international journal for our readers to trial to read which may be expending their effectiveness with the similar readers and others too. On contrast, the GDP will effect the research and development progression because the good experimental conditions may produce excellent results meanwhile, on the contrary the excellent R &D (research and development) may improve the economy GDP enhancement since the high technology may form high efficiency &profit. Not only depending the independent contents but also depending collaboration between our partners from up and down ones, both of them need to produce innovation course. The high-technique level will play a more important results as a GDP enhancement factor like PC business which may become an essential tool for us to wield its strong usefulness in university and maker specially in R &D department design and innovation. Therefore, the corresponding Master and Doctor will wield their smart spirituality to continually process their items with more sophisticate research and calculation to predict and judge definitely.

Funding

This paper was supported by Korean Science and Engineering under the granted No. 96-0300-11-01-03 with the specified Basis Research program.

Ethic Declarations

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest.

References

1. Suintextreviews.org
2. E-Mail, Sep. 10, 2025
3. Tencent News, Wechat, Sep. 10, 2025, Internet
4. Tencent News, Wechat, Sep. 11, 2025, Internet
5. E-Mail, Sep. 12, 2025
6. Tencent News, Wechat, Sep. 16, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17774767

7. E-Mail, Sep. 14, 2025
8. VIP-manager, Morning plate's main-line dragon-head, Wechat, Sep. 16, 2025, Internet
9. Xueliang Peng, Nine aspects cloud capturing dragon, Wechat, Sep. 16, 2025
10. TOPCJ, Wechat, Sep. 11, 2025
11. Run Xu, The Relationship of Properties with Variable Mass of Block on Crank Linkage Mechanism in Multibody System, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021,S1: 105 **Crossref,Google scholar, Scilit**
12. Run Xu, Boyong Hur, A Simulation between Torque and Angle with Speed on Five Freedoms of Robot Mechanical Arm in Multibody Systems, Saudi Journal of Civil Engineering, 2021, 5(5): 91~93 **Impact factor 1.2**
13. Run Xu, Boyong Hur, The Relationship between Force and Time with Lagrange Equation by Regulating Piston Mass on Crankshaft of Vehicle, Saudi Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2021,6(4): 73-76 **Impact factor 1.2**
14. Run Xu, Jiaguang Liu, The Kinematics Model Establishment of Crank and Linkage with Time under Low Speed in Vehicle, 2021,6(4):67~72,Saudi Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2021,6(4): 57~61, DOI: 10.36348/sjet,2021,v06i04,004 **Impact factor 1.2**
15. Run Xu, The Kinematic Models of Crank with Angle and Time in Motor Housing Process, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021, S1: 104, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51737/2766-5100,2021,S1,004> **Impact factor 2.6, Scilit, Crossref, Google Scholar**
16. Run Xu, Boyong Hur, The Relationship between Force and Time with Lagrange Equation by Regulating Piston Mass on Crankshaft of Vehicle, Saudi Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2021,6(4): 73-76 **Impact factor 1.2**
17. Run Xu, Jiaguang Liu, The Kinematics Model Establishment of Crank and Linkage with Time under Low Speed in Vehicle, 2021,6(4):67~72,Saudi Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2021,6(4): 57~61, DOI: 10.36348/sjet,2021,v06i04,004 **Impact factor 1.2**
18. Run Xu, The Kinematic Models of Crank with Angle and Time in Motor Housing Process, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021, S1: 104, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51737/2766-5100,2021,S1,004> **Impact factor 2.6, Scilit, Crossref, Google Scholar**
19. Run Xu, The Modelling between Force & Torque and Crank Angle on Crank Linkage of Engine in Vehicle by Lagrange Formula I, Scholars International Journal of Chemistry and Material Sciences, 2021, 4(4): 36-39,DOI: 10.36348/sijcms,2021,v04i04,005
20. Run Xu, The Dynamic Modelling of Vortex Axis Blade between Speed, Force and Rotation under Variable Angle & Power in Helicopter, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021,S1: 103 **Impact factor 2.6, Scilit, Crossref, Google Scholar**
21. Run Xu, The Study of Relationship between Current and Acceleration on Simulation in Motor, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021, S1: 101, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.51737/2766-5100,2021,S1,001> **Impact factor 2.6, Scilit, Crossref, Google Scholar**